

Manifestation of Thoughts with History and Literature in the Indian Knowledge System

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Abstract

A brief introduction about the advent of English language and British literature in India by establishment of Empire rule and the way it has condemned the Indian languages and literature. This paper pays an attention to make changes for the shifting of British literature to Indian literature under the domain of Indian Knowledge System to make Indian literature more Indian in nature by inculcating Indian literary text such as retelling of mythologies with modernity, postcolonial literature, theories etc. of renowned Indian authors. It will trace the relevancy of Indian Knowledge System in the contemporary scenario and also look upon the importance of the National Education Policy 2020 implemented by the Government of India.

Keywords: Postcolonial, Indian Knowledge System, National Education Policy, Literature, History

Introduction

“We owe a lot to the ancient Indians, teaching us how to count. Without which most modern scientific discoveries would have been impossible” – Albert Einstein

Antecedently before Empire rule has established in India, portray the rich history, culture, society and literary text. The intellects had discovered and postulated the traditional theories and principles in all the spheres- literature, governance, philosophy, sociology (dharmaśāstra), architecture, logic, biology, trade and commerce, geography, economy, science, military, medicine and history which has been treasured in the form of literary text. However, from the advent of Europeans, the traditional skills and practices were gradually began to dissipate and were forced to indulge in new principles and skills which was based on unfamiliar practices and were radical in nature such as plantation of coffee, indigo etc. Among these two distinct phases of vanishing and upcoming of new things, the traditional knowledge system has lost its glory in the eve of colonialism and encountered the European modernity. Thus, the concept of classical Indian thought was untouched, unspoken, unquestioned and unanswered for many years after the Independence.

The United Nations defines ‘Traditional Knowledge System’ as: “Traditional knowledge or local knowledge is a record of human achievement in comprehending the complexities of life and survival in often unfriendly environments. Traditional knowledge, which may be technical, social, organizational, or cultural, was obtained as part of the great human experiment of survival and development.” Indian Knowledge System can be understood broadly as the knowledge and skills originated on the home land of India. The knowledge, skill, belief and practice that an indigenous people and community has developed over a long period of time and the process to preserve and propagate the traditional knowledge to new generation for years and years is depicted as Indian Knowledge Tradition.

A Postcolonial Exploration of History and Literature in Indian Knowledge System

Indian history accorded immense richness, glory and legacy. It draws the symbol of unity in diversity. The time line of Indian history starts from the early Neolithic period till today’s date and so the Indian Literature has been formed simultaneously which acquired the major events, art forms, socio- cultural realities, traditions, customs etc. Hence, History and Literature are intertwined with each other, where History is the gateway to go into the past whereas Literature is considered as mirror of the society. This research is based on the multidisciplinary subject and will explore the importance of Indian Literature and Language which was written and originated ages before the arrival of British in India and even in contemporary times. It is to

highlight how the emergence of Europeans have distorted the Indian culture, art forms, traditional knowledge, society, history and as well as literature.

The main aim of this research paper is to highlight the importance of Indian Knowledge System and to acknowledge the Indian literature written in English and the literature translated in English from various other Indian languages to our youth and to embrace the classic learning. It is to highlight the New World Literature as a non-Eurocentric literary system which will transcend the national boundaries. The intent of paper deals with the necessity of paradigm shift from British literature to Indian literature. It will help in channelizing the thoughts and views of India's new generation towards the traditional theories and skills. This will help them to feel connected with our culture, tradition, custom etc in modern times. Thus, it is important for us to expand, preserve, propagate and proliferating the texts, ideas, thoughts and theories of our indigenous intellects. This research paper will explore the socio-cultural realities and literary text of pre-colonial literature as well as postcolonial literature, which can improve and better the understanding of problems faced by society and humanity today and to tackle with them efficiently with traditional plus modern approach.

Notable author Kipling has once said, the Europeans depicted it was their responsibility 'white man's burden' to civilize east; they tried orientals to realize their incapability, lack of potential, black skinned and barbarians. But we must not forget our roots that we are civilized from the Harappa Civilization dated back 3300-1300 BCE. The Indus Script is one of the earliest known writing systems, but it remains undeciphered. India has rich heritage, culture and history since then which is delineated from our known literatures such as Ramayana, Mahabharata, Vedas, Upanishads, and Inscriptions etc. written in Sanskrit language. Then we also have Buddhist and Jainism literature which were produced in Gandhari language, Pali, Prakrit and Sanskrit. Arrival of Britishers in Indian subcontinent around 16th century tried to impose imperialism, afterwards which took the shape of colonialism. The then, advent of British Raj introduced the new language 'English' into the Indian Territory. English language and literature gradually put its step through the passing of Charter Act of 1813. In 1835, Minutes of Thomas Babington Macaulay was produced which ambushed Indian history, literature and culture. He condemns the teachings of Indian languages such as Sanskrit, Persian and other vernacular languages. Instead, he emphasized on the learning of English literature and language. He once said, "Indian in blood and colour, but English in taste, in opinions, in morals, and in intellect".

The "Magna Carta of English Education in India," also known as the "Wood's Dispatch", in 1854 was introduced. It created a gateway for English literary text in the educational system of India. Many universities were opened based on the framework of English. These stepping stones altogether decayed the Indian literature and languages. Mahatma Gandhi wrote in The Indian Opinion that "English must be learnt, but one's mother-tongue should not be ignored".

The European rule ended after 200 years with great freedom struggle. In the eve of Independence, we got liberated politically but left shattered and broken from inside the heart. This left the minds of Indian people colonized and still it is deeply rooted, which is reflected in their writings written in English or in other languages. The supremacy of English language has weekend the glory of Indian languages. Language is known as the medium of communication whether spoken or written in English or in vernacular languages.

In the contemporary scenario, English has its relevancy despite being related to colonial legacy. Due to globalization, English is the only language which connects the India on the international platform. It acts as a medium for the growth and opportunities for the people who have knowledge of English language. It is important to acknowledge the significance of Indian traditional system of Indian literature written in English or in various other languages. It is high time to make a paradigm shift of the Eurocentric literature to Indian literature or New World literature of Decolonized Indian.

In the modern day, new generation is far away from the Indian mythologies, cultures, traditions and moral values because they have a great impact of western culture. Thus, it is prominent to bring our ancient, Vedic, medieval and modern Indian literature in the main stream which will connect our youth to the Indian Traditional System. Various literary authors, such as R. K. Narayan, Girish Karnad, Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, Ashwin Singhai, Dev Dutt Patanaya, and Krishna Uday Shankar have written and produced their masterpiece which does the immense work of retelling of mythologies such as Ramayana, Mahabharata, and Bhagavad Gita in English language. Such works should be an integral part of the academics from the early age. It is easy to study because these are written in English with the twist of modernity. In this way it will connect and help us to understand the Indian tradition, skills, knowledge, customs, and will lend a hand to overcome from colonial hegemony effortlessly.

We have addressed above, Literature as mirror of the society. Novels like *Swami and Friends*, *The Guide*, *Two Leaves and a Bud*, *Untouchable*, *Coolie*, *Kanthapura*, *Interpreter of Maldives*, *Midnight's Children*, *Cry the Peacock*, *The God of Small Things*, *The Shadow Lines*, *The Hungry Tide*, *The Glass Palace* etc. are the works which exhibits the real image of the society in the reel stories. These fiction novels shares the common motifs of colonialism such as immigration, exile, dominions, color, creed, quest for identity, racism, caste discrimination, familial relationships, gender inequality etc. which is still prevalent in the society and have to take an account to encounter them. It is true, that for the growth of individual, he must be aware about the existence of social evils around him and should strengthen their roots and must preserve them to overcome from all such issues by the practical application.

The eminent postcolonial authors such as R. K. Narayan, Raja Rao, Mulk Raj Anand and contemporary writers like Amitav Ghosh, Amit Choudhary, Salman Rushdie are continuously working on the themes of postcolonialism. They have contributed a lot to the Indian society, through their literature and have even marked an important place in the western world. Today, the women writers like Arundhati Roy, Bharti Mukherjee, Kiran Desai before that we have Kamala Markandaya, Nayantara Sahgal, Anita Desai have much talked about the sufferings and discrimination of women in their novels. Further, the prominent foreign writers from the decolonized nations such as Chinua Achebe, J. M. Coetzee, George Lamming, Abdulrazak Gurnah, Patrick White, Jean Rhys, David Malouf, Carol Shield, Margaret Laurence and many more have touched and shared the experiences of colonialism from there notable works.

A famous Indian author Gauri Vishwanathan in her novel *Mask of Conquest: Literary Study and British Rule in India* (1999) exemplified as classic work in the area of postcolonial studies. She brings light on the establishment of English Studies in India under British rule and describes the degradation of Indian languages. Likewise, a renowned female foreign novelist Jamaica Kincaid from British Colony- Antigua in her novel *Small Place* draws her experience and expressed the way Empire rule have decayed their culture, literature and territory. She also focuses upon the English Educational system implemented which tried to turn local people into Englishmen. Hence two different authors of different geographical regions share the common experience in respective works which evident the above-mentioned problem faced by the colonized nations and the literary text.

The postcolonial theorists like Edward W. Said, Frantz Fanon, Homi k. Bhabha and Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak pioneered postcolonial theories like Hybridity, Diaspora, Ambivalence, Mimicry, Subaltern, Orientalism etc. These theories are used to critically analyze the novels on the lens of postcolonialism which deduce the modern-day postcolonial trends like trans culturalism, neomadism, cosmopolitan etc. it relates the relevancy of decolonizing the minds of the colonized nations. These theorists have also tried to correlate postcolonial literature with other fields like sociology, philosophy, history, cultural and literary traditions to make it a trans-disciplinary subject and its importance in modern day society. Thus, postcolonial Indian literature comes under the domain of Indian Knowledge System because the main purpose of IKS is to promote interdisciplinary research, preservation and propagation of rich heritage of our country.

In this paper we have looked upon the arrival of English literature and language in India by the Europeans to assert the legacy. The aim of this study is to explore the Indian literature in English and other languages under the Indian Knowledge System and to inculcate them in the academics to promote the literary text, history, culture and rich heritage of Indian society. It also intends to analyze the socio- cultural realities from text, which can improve and better the understanding of problems faced by society and humanity today. The methodology of this paper is descriptive, critical and psychoanalytical in nature to study both history and literature simultaneously.

The felicitousness of Indian Knowledge System can be examined from the event- Azadi Ka Amrit Mahotsav or 75th Anniversary of Indian Independence celebrated by Government of India. It is the initiative to celebrate and honored the day of Independence from the British Raj and the history of India's people freedom movement, culture, literary text and achievements. Under this program Union Education Minister Dharmendra Pradhan launched the textbook on the occasion of Buddha Purnima. The book titled *Introduction to Indian Knowledge System: Concepts and Application*, has the main focus on engineering and technology but it will also address other fields such as arts and literature, architecture, management, economics etc. Addressing the event, he expressed his happiness and gratitude showed towards the writers of above-mentioned book and said, "Indian Knowledge System holds solution to many of the world's challenges". He also talked about the ancient history, Vedas, Upanishads, and other Indian texts. He added by saying, "Our

ancient heritage is full of treasure which needs to be preserved, documented and propagated. While we adopt good things from our ancient past, we must also be mindful of the problems in our society and build a future which creates synergy between knowledge from the past and contemporary issues”.

Conclusion

The New Education Policy 2020 (NEP) gives a clear vision for disseminating Indian Knowledge System in the higher education curriculum and making necessary a book of such kind in educational institutions across the country in forth coming years. Thus, now it is time to do the respective changes in the Indian English literature and to make it more Indian in its nature. Now, we can say that, subjects of social science and humanities moves parallelly and gives this research paper multidisciplinary perspective. Finally, the conclusions will be made to study the rich history and the Literature written in different languages and in English in Indian subcontinent. Look forward to rejuvenate our past history and literature to open the way for upcoming generations to create our own indigenous and traditional system and opt a path for sustainable growth to leave far behind the concept of colonization from our colonial mind- set.

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